

ELECTRO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CONDUCTIVE EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The electrical resistivity of epoxy composites is studied during curing and upon heating of the cured material. The initial resistivity ρ of epoxy containing a metallic filler is in the range of 10^6 to $10^7 \Omega\text{cm}$. During curing a sudden reduction of ρ by *eight orders of magnitude* is observed. The shrinkage of the polymer during cross-linking and the build-up of internal stresses results in a lower inter-particle contact resistance. The contraction can be reversed by heating up again. Around curing temperature, the resistivity increases by *six to eight orders of magnitude* due to the expansion of the material. The resistivity increases progressively until the contacts between the particles are opened and the composite reaches a high-ohmic state.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials become more and more important in electrotechnology. Development based on conventional materials has been driven so far that only minor improvements can still be expected. Technology jumps need new material properties. This can be expected from composites. As it has already been shown, the combination of two materials can result in new, under some circumstances, even smart material properties [1 - 4].

For the commercial use of functional composites, a complete understanding of their properties is necessary. Some attempts have been made to model the electrical resistivity of composites [5, 6]. But for applications as chemical sensors [6], pressure sensors [7, 8] or thermistors [9 - 11] the combination and cooperation of micro-mechanical and electrical properties are of crucial importance. In the case of thermistors based on a semi-crystalline polymer matrix, the positive temperature coefficient (PTC) of resistance is generally attributed to the relatively large change in specific volume of the polymer at its melting temperature [10, 12]. This has led to the development of commercial current sensors or limiters by Raychem, Burns etc. and for high power ratings by ABB Control (PROLIM[®][13]). On the other hand, the nature of the PTC effect in amorphous polymer composites, e.g. epoxy composites, could not be explained in previous work [9 - 11].

In the present work, the electrical resistivity of conductive epoxy composites during curing and upon heating of the cured material was studied. By combination with dilatometry, the resistivity could be related to the contraction or expansion of the polymer. In order to explore the mechanical action of the polymer matrix and to avoid superimposed effects from soft particle-particle contacts, a hard metallic filler (e.g. TiB_2 [6]) was used.

EXPERIMENTAL

The commercial powder from Cerac Inc. had a broad particle size distribution between $40\ \mu\text{m}$ – $200\ \mu\text{m}$ and was sieved to particle sizes between $63\ \mu\text{m}$ and $100\ \mu\text{m}$. Polycrystalline TiB_2 has an electrical resistivity of about $15\ \mu\Omega\text{cm}$ at room temperature [14]. For its linear thermal expansion coefficient, values between $4.8 \cdot 10^{-6}\ \text{K}^{-1}$ and $(8 - 9.5) \cdot 10^{-6}\ \text{K}^{-1}$ have been reported [15, 16].

A low viscosity epoxy called Spurr B, obtained from Polysciences Inc., was used as the matrix material. During the curing of epoxy composites, inhomogeneities in the composition quite often occur due to settling of the filler particles. In order to avoid these inhomogeneities, we restricted our work to high filler fractions determined by the density of the settled particles close to the tap density of the powder. The TiB_2 powder was tapped into a Teflon mold, degassed in slight vacuum at 50 mbar for 30 min. and infiltrated in situ with the epoxy. The composite was then cured for 15 h at 80°C , 100°C , 120°C or 140°C by placing the samples in the preheated oven. The cured epoxy composite had a filler content of about 46 vol. %. In order to measure the electrical resistivity during the curing process, four contact pins were embedded in the powder bed before infiltration. The resistance was measured by the four-point method using a Keithley 195 A digital multimeter. A thermocouple was also embedded in the powder / epoxy mixture and monitored the temperature in the composite.

The glass transition temperature and the thermal expansion coefficients of the cured material were determined by a Perkin Elmer DSC 7 Differential Scanning Calorimeter and a Perkin Elmer DMA 7 Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer, respectively. The dependence of the resistivity on temperature was tested using a Novocontrol Broadband Dielectric Spectrometer (incl. HP 4247 A Impedance Analyzer and Temperature Control). The composites were cut into pieces of (2 - 5) mm x (2 - 5) mm x 30 mm and contacted by four stripes of air-dried silver paint. For the four-point measurements, spring tips were pressed onto the stripes of silver.

The expansion and contraction of the pure epoxy during the curing process was measured using a glass pipette of about 1 m length and 11 mm diameter. The cold epoxy was filled into the pipette

Figure 1. Relative thermal expansion and temperature of epoxy during curing at 80°C as a function of time.

together with a thermocouple for temperature control. Then the pipette was placed in a hot oven and the height of the epoxy column was controlled as a function of time. This works well for the gelation process. When the epoxy becomes rigid, the internal stresses are released via cracks and no change in volume can be observed anymore.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The relative thermal expansion and the temperature of unfilled epoxy cured at 80°C are plotted as a function of time in Fig. 1. Within 12 min. the epoxy is heated up to 80°C. During this period the epoxy expands by 5 %. Then it starts to shrink and passes the initial volume after 50 min., while the temperature has increased to a maximum value of 92°C. The epoxy contracts further to a final value of about -2.5 % after 3 h and the temperature decreases to 82°C.

The deflection in the expansion curve indicates that cross-linking of the epoxy starts around 80°C and results in the volume reduction of the epoxy. The overshoot of the temperature above ambient temperature is due to the heat of reaction, which is released. The heating stops when the epoxy has reached its final volume.

For curing at 140°C, the maximum expansion of the epoxy is reached after 9 min. at an internal temperature of 160°C. The temperature then further increases to a maximum value of 184°C, while the epoxy already reduces its volume. After 20 min. the first cracks occurred at a relative expansion of 6 % before the shrinkage of the epoxy was finished. At this high temperature the curing process is of course much faster. But this also implies that the local temperature differences in the epoxy are stronger and thus mechanical stresses become quite high.

Fig. 2 shows the specific resistivity ρ and the internal temperature of an epoxy / 46 vol. % TiB₂ composite during curing at 100°C. The initial resistivity is $4 \times 10^6 \Omega\text{cm}$. While the temperature of

Figure 2. Spurr B epoxy / 43 vol% TiB₂ during curing at 100 °C: specific resistivity (plain line) and temperature (dashed line)

the epoxy-powder mixture increases to 93°C within 30 min., ρ is reduced to $6 \times 10^4 \Omega \text{ cm}$. But then the resistivity increases again to a peak value of $2.5 \times 10^6 \Omega \text{ cm}$ (45 min.). Within 10 min. the resistivity is then reduced by *eight orders of magnitude*. The temperature increases in the meantime to a maximum of 106°C. After a curing time of 75 min., ρ has stabilized at about $0.04 \Omega \text{ cm}$ and the temperature at 102°C. These values are stable and unchanged till the end of curing after 15 h. During the slow cool-down, a further reduction of the resistivity by a factor of four is observed and the highly-loaded composite ends up with a $\rho \approx 0.01 \Omega \text{ cm}$.

Surprisingly, the initial resistivity is quite high, although the filler particles have metallic conductivity and the filler fraction corresponds to the tap density. But also tapped TiB_2 powder has a $\rho > 10^7 \Omega \text{ cm}$. It seems that the contact pressure between the particles in loose powder is too small. Wetted by epoxy, a thin epoxy films can additionally exist between the particles. The reduction of the resistivity during the first 30 min. is due to an increasing conductivity of the epoxy resin with temperature, as measured on pure epoxy, too, where the resistivity decreases by about one order of magnitude between 30°C and 80°C. The increase starting at a temperature of about 80°C may have two reasons. During gelation the resistivity of epoxy generally increases. Secondly, a separation of the particles occurs due to the expansion of the epoxy, as observed for the pure epoxy (Fig. 1). Subsequently, the sudden reduction of the resistivity is correlated to the shrinkage of the epoxy, which increases the particle-particle pressure. Thereby thin epoxy films between the particles can be penetrated. Taking as a guideline the data for curing at 80°C (Fig. 1), the unfilled epoxy shrinks by about 7.5 % between the point of highest expansion and the cured state. For the 46 vol% filled composite, the resulting shrinkage should be about half of this value, since the thermal expansion of TiB_2 is comparably small. Assuming a mean particle size of 80 μm , the gap between two particles should be reduced in average by $\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$ during this shrinkage. At the same time the resistivity decreases by eight orders of magnitude.

As observed for the pure epoxy, the internal temperature increases during the gelation process because of the heat of reaction. When the sample cools down at the end of the curing process, a further reduction in resistivity is caused by the thermal contraction of the composite.

Fig. 3 shows the resistivity monitored during curing at different temperatures T_{cure} . Qualitatively, the behavior is similar for all temperatures. However, with increasing T_{cure} , the time until the resistivity peak occurs becomes shorter. Also the maximum resistivity value becomes smaller. At $T_{\text{cure}} = 80^\circ\text{C}$, ρ could not be detected for some time since it was out of the measuring range. It is clear that with higher temperature the gelation starts earlier. Obviously for 140°C it is so fast that the material is heated up inhomogeneously and cannot be fully expanded before the curing starts. Therefore, the resistivity peak is smaller. It should be mentioned that the relatively long time until the gelation started in the composite (100 min. vs. 12 min. for the pure epoxy at 80°C) is due to the massy Teflon mold which we used compared to the slim glass pipette.

Figure 3. Specific resistivity of Spurr B epoxy / 46 vol% TiB_2 during curing at 80 °C, 100 °C, 120 °C and 140 °C

Figure 4. Thermal expansion of Spurr B epoxy cured at 80°C and 140°C and Spurr B epoxy / 46 vol% TiB₂ composites cured at 80°C and 80°C, 100°C, 120°C and 140°C.

Fig. 4 shows the thermal expansion of the composites cured at different temperatures in comparison to pure epoxy cured at 80°C and 140°C. As expected from a simple mixing rule, the thermal expansion of the composites is smaller than the expansion of the pure epoxy. But surprisingly, the expansion coefficient *decreases* with higher curing temperature for the composites, but not for the epoxy. The thermal expansion coefficients α are given in Table 1.

The expansion is not dominated by the glass transition temperature T_g , as one might expect. T_g measured by DSC is for all materials roughly the same (~80°C) as seen from Table 2. For curing at 140°C, it is even a bit smaller. At high T_{cure} the reaction of the epoxy is very fast. Not all monomers find reactive partners, thus the number of links per volume is smaller and T_g is lower. This effect is mainly apparent for $T_{cure} = 140^\circ\text{C}$. In the composite, a decrease of the anhydride hardener content can be caused by a hydratization to dicarbon acid due to water adsorbed or chemically bonded to the TiB₂ surface (e.g. H₃BO₃). This would reduce T_g as well. And in fact, T_g is slightly smaller for the composite than for the unfilled epoxy.

A possible explanation for the reduction of α is as follows. At high curing temperatures the epoxy resin is expanded to a higher absolute volume. In this state, cross-linking starts and fixes this volume. During gelation, the pure epoxy can contract freely whereas the shrinkage is hindered by the filler particles in the composite and stresses are built up at the interface between epoxy

Table 1. Thermal expansion coefficients

α (10 ⁻⁴ K ⁻¹)	Spurr B cured at		Spurr B / TiB ₂ Composites cured at			
	80°C	140°C	80°C	100°C	120°C	140°C
T = 30°C - 90°C	1.18	1.37	0.68	0.74	0.48	0.34
T = 90°C - 170°C	1.91	1.95	1.14	1.08	0.94	0.83

Table 2. Measured glass transition temperatures (averaged)

Curing temperature T_{cure} (°C)	Spurr B T_g (°C)	Spurr / TiB ₂ (46%) T_g (°C)
80	80	84
100	93	88
120	83	89
140	75	71

and particle surface. When the material cools down after curing, the cross-linked epoxy tries to keep the expanded volume. The densely packed filler particles and the interfacial stresses help to stabilize this structure, whereas the pure epoxy shrinks freely. This is supported by exact measurements of the densities, which are shown in Table 3. The density decreases with increasing T_{cure} . When the material is heated up again, the stresses are maintained until the curing temperature is reached. The stresses suppress the thermal expansion and hence the high T_{cure} material has a lower expansion coefficient.

The contraction during curing and the related reduction in resistivity can be reversed by heating-up again. Fig. 5 shows the temperature dependence of the resistivity of the cured composites in

Table 3. Mass densities

mass density	Spurr B cured at		Spurr B / TiB ₂ Composites cured at			
	80°C	140°C	80°C	100°C	120°C	140°C
ρ_{mass} (g/cm ³)	1.09	1.10	2.70	2.69	2.67	2.65

Figure 5. Specific resistivity of Spurr B cured at 80 °C and 140 °C and Spurr B epoxy / 46 vol% TiB₂ composites cured at 80 °C, 100 °C, 120 °C and 140 °C as a function of temperature.

Figure 6. Specific resistivity plotted vs. relative expansion for Spurr B epoxy / 43 vol. % TiB_2 cured for 15 h at 80°C, 100°C, and 140°C. Resistivity and relative expansion were measured separately as a function of temperature.

comparison to epoxy. The cold resistance of the composites is in the range of 0.005 - 0.015 Ωcm . Around T_{cure} , ρ increases by seven to nine orders of magnitude and remains stable on a level of 10^6 - $10^8 \Omega\text{cm}$ for higher temperatures. Between 30°C and 180°C the resistivity of the pure epoxy decreases from 10^{15} - $10^{17} \Omega\text{cm}$ down to 10^8 - $10^{10} \Omega\text{cm}$ but is still considerably higher than in the composite. This shows that the composite is dominated by the inter-particle contacts rather than the insulating properties of the epoxy. The transition from the conducting state to the high-resistive state is caused by the thermal expansion. In Fig. 6 the specific resistivity (measured as a function of temperature) is plotted versus the relative expansion (at same temperatures). For curing temperatures between 100°C and 140°C, the increase of ρ occurs at a constant expansion of 0.6 %. Only for $T_{\text{cure}} = 80^\circ\text{C}$, an expansion of 0.3 % is already sufficient for the increase of ρ . The resistivity increases progressively until the contacts between the particles are opened. A certain particle distance is necessary to reach the high-ohmic state. For a mean particle size of 80 μm , an expansion by 0.6 % means an average inter-particle gap of 400 nm. It is not quite clear why for $T_{\text{cure}} = 80^\circ\text{C}$ this situation is already achieved for a smaller expansion. Perhaps the curing is not really finished in this case.

CONCLUSION

Our experiments have shown that thermal contraction and expansion of composites can have a huge influence on the electrical resistivity. Since a filler fraction of 46 % is far beyond the percolation threshold ($\approx 17\%$), this effect can not be explained in terms of percolation theory. Also, it has been shown that it is not related to the phase transition of the epoxy at the glass transition temperature.

Instead, our experiments indicate that the observed strong resistivity changes are caused by the particle-particle contacts, in particular the change in gap distance, and the thermo-mechanical properties of the polymer matrix. The epoxy / TiB_2 composite serves as a kind of model system.

Due to the hardness of TiB_2 , the particle contacts do not deform or weld together and make the resistivity of the composite sensitive to small micro-mechanical changes. Therefore, this system can be very useful in order to understand the conduction mechanism in electro-active composites.

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